

SURVEILLANCE CARD_ Tick-borne encephalitis (TBE)_Pathogen detection in raw milk from domestic ruminants (cattle, sheep and goats) in high-risk regions

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Pathogen detection in raw milk samples from domestic ruminants (cattle, sheep and goats) in high-risk regions.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of an increase in incidence; Early detection of the introduction of the pathogen; early detection of the disease in milk.
3	Target species and group	Domestic ruminants (cattle, sheep and goats).
4	Target sector / production type	Dairy animals.
5	Geographical area covered	High-risk regions that were already identified with a high prevalence of the disease in the past; areas with a high prevalence of ticks; pasture areas of ruminants, bordering wooded areas.
6	Age group	Animals which have already reached the first lactation; greater than 7-10 months of age.
7	Sampling point and strategy	On farm; a given number of milk samples are collected from a predetermined number of farms in a given area identified in each MS due to the previous high prevalence of the disease. Sampling is carried out on bulk milk from each individual farm.
8	Sampling time period	Year-round / not limited. May to November is the period with the highest prevalence registered of the disease in EU.
9	Sampling matrix	Raw milk collected from bulk milk in tanks pooled from multiple animals in a herd. (1)
10	Type of disease indicators	Presence of the pathogen - Identification of the agent.
11	Sampling unit	A minimum 50-mL samples taken from the bulk milk tanks. (1)
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Lactating domestic ruminants.
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Real-Time Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT- PCR). (2)

14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Only applicable if the sampling protocol ensures a representative sample (see 16)
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	To be defined and reported. Ideally 95 %.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	This activity targets a known population and the sensitivity of detection can be calculated if the sampling protocol ensures a representative sample, which can be achieved by different sampling strategies, including for instance random, stratified, or risk-based. Estimation of the sensitivity in the latter case depends on proper definition of the risk strata and their relative risks. The component is expected to have a high sensitivity (4)
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Q-fever, Brucella spp., Leptospirosis. (5)
18	References	<p>1) OIE Terrestrial Manual 2018, Chapter 1.1.2. Collection, submission and storage of diagnostic specimens.</p> <p>2) Paulsen KM, Stuen S, das Neves CG, Suhel F, Gurung D, Soleng A, Stiasny K, Vikse R, Andreassen ÅK, Granquist EG. Tick-borne encephalitis virus in cows and unpasteurized cow milk from Norway. Zoonoses Public Health. 2019 Mar;66(2):216-222. doi: 10.1111/zph.12554. Epub 2018 Dec 28. PMID: 30593734.</p> <p>3) Cisak E, Wójcik-Fatla A, Zając V, Sroka J, Buczek A, Dutkiewicz J. Prevalence of tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBEV) in samples of raw milk taken randomly from cows, goats and sheep in eastern Poland. Ann Agric Environ Med. 2010;17(2):283-6. PMID: 21186771.</p> <p>4) WOAHP Flavivirus (causing tick borne encephalitis) (Infection with) Technical disease card – Terrestrial Manual, 2020</p> <p>5) Maria A.S.MoreiraAbelardo SilvaJúniorMagna C.LimaSanely L.da Costa - Chapter 11 - Infectious Diseases in Dairy Cattle, 2018</p>
19	Additional comments	Prevalence information available: 20.7%. (3)

